

IMPLICATIONS OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON ADOLESCENT AND YOUTH BEHAVIOR IN URBAN ENVIRONMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Social media has become a dependency in society, especially among teenagers and youth. So that social media has a big influence on changing the behavior of adolescents and youth. From the positive and negative impacts. According to Crish Garrett (2009: 78) social media is a tool, service and communication that facilitates relationships between people with one another and has many enthusiasts including teenagers, even minors who already have personal social media accounts. In the current social conditions the use of social media is loved by all ages. Especially youth and adolescents have their own values which have an element of domination in the use of this tool. The purpose of this research is to find out the implications of social media that have an impact on the psychological side of young people in urban areas. Research using descriptive research with the form of case study research. The object of research is teenagers and youth in the urban area of Samarinda from various campuses and schools. The results of the study show that social media has facilitated many conveniences for life, and also has a large positive and negative impact on society, especially teenagers and young people. The positive impact on social interaction is connectivity, the benefits of being connected to each other with anyone regardless of distance, time, religion or country, being able to get the latest news or information quickly, and being able to explore and develop himself with the information he has obtained from social media. The negative impacts of using social media are lack of caring for others, causing internet addiction, ease of interaction causing lazy socializing and conveying messages directly, impolite and speaking and attitude, lack of self-control of adolescents to maintain their privacy, giving rise to verbal violence, cyberbullying, data theft privacy, sexting to sexual violence, mental health disorders such as Internet Addiction Disorder, Nomophobia and also sleep disorders due to excessive use.

KEY WORDS:

Implications, Social Media, Teenagers, Youth, Urban Areas

INTRODUCTION

Information technology is inseparable from the process of human communication as social beings. Information technology is required to always create new things in facilitating the process of human communication. Information technology is considered capable of creating and empowering a more effective communication process.

The development of information technology brings a change in society. The birth of social media makes people's behavior patterns experience a shift in culture, ethics and existing norms. Indonesia with a large population with various ethnic, racial and religious cultures has a lot of potential for social change.

The 2019 Global Digital data conducted by We Are Social (Wearesocial.com, 2019) states that there has been an increase in the use of social media compared to 2018, and its use is dominated by young people in Indonesia's Y and Z generations, namely between 18-34 years old. This research was conducted from January 2018 to January 2019. The research shows that the use of social media is dominated by male users rather than female users. Male users 18-24 years dominate by 18 percent compared to women by 15 percent. Meanwhile, for ages 25-34 years, men still dominate with 19 percent and women 14 percent of the total users (kompas.com, 2019).

Social media exists as a combination of communication flows with technological developments. Social media is an online platform that people use to build social networks or social relationships with other people who have interests, group activities, or personal activities or interactions in the same career (Akram and Kumar, 2017).

Currently social media is in great demand by users of internet facilities because social media makes it easy for users to find someone. The search is not only for people who are known but also people who are not known or it can also be said just to add friends or relations. The use of social media is not limited to certain groups, but this facility can be used by all groups, professions and ages. Its easy use makes people enjoy this facility. Because its users are not limited to circles, professions and parents, but also children, teenagers and young people.

Adolescents and youth have used information technology facilities, namely cellphones that have internet facilities, with which they can open their social media anytime and anywhere. The various social media facilities make its users really enjoy and make them always want to be in touch with this information technology, especially among the youth. They can use several applications at the same time, so it's no wonder that many teenagers and young people always spend time using gadgets and places that can access the internet such as campuses, schools and cafes to be able to use facilities or open social media which is often said with "online".

In January 2021 Indonesia is included in the top 10 countries with people in 9th order addicted to social media. Around 170 million people have used the internet and social media actively, with the time spent by Indonesians per day for 8 hours 52 minutes. Applications that are widely used are YouTube, WhatsApp, Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, Tiktok, Video Streaming such as Netflix, Viu and others are also increasing in use (We are social digital 2020 July Global Statshot Report).

This social media facility has also become a hot topic of conversation both within the school environment and outside the school environment. The use of social media has two opposite sides for

the psychological development of adolescents and youth, especially those living in urban areas. Because urban areas will have a big impact, with the very rapid development of social media.

The purpose of this research is to find out the implications of social media that have an impact on the psychological side of young people in urban areas.

THEORY

Social media is a channel or means of online social interaction in cyberspace (internet). Social media users communicate by interacting with each other by sending messages, sharing and building networks (Nasrullah, 2015). Sharing and creating content includes blogs, wiki social networks, forums, and virtual worlds. Blogs, social networks and wikis are the most common forms of social media used by people around the world. Andreas Kaplan and Harlein (2010) define social media as "a group of internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0, and which enable the creation and exchange of user-generated content". Social networks are sites where everyone creates a personal web page and then connects with friends to share information and communicate. The largest social networks include Facebook, Myspace, WhatsApp, BBM, Youtube, Line, Instagram and Twitter. If traditional media uses print media and broadcast media, then social media uses the internet. Social media invites anyone who is interested to participate by making contributions and feedback openly, making comments and sharing information in a fast and unlimited time. As Vivian Sobcack writes, an American author says: "TV, video cassette, video tape player/recorder, video games and personal computer (PC) all form an overall electronic system whose various forms of 'interface' constitute an alternative world and absolute which uniquely includes the audience/user in a space that is not centered is temporary and has an apparent form.

Behavior is the result of all kinds of experience and human interaction with the environment which is manifested in the form of knowledge, attitudes and actions. behavior is an individual's response/reaction to stimuli that come from outside and from within him (Notoatmodjo, 2010).

Behavior is a function of individual characteristics and the environment. Individual characteristics include various variables such as motives, values, traits, personality, and attitudes that interact with each other and then also interact with environmental factors in determining behavior. Environmental factors have great power in determining behavior, even the power is greater than individual characteristics (Azwar, 2010).

According to Lohrmann et al (2008), with the theory of behavior change The Ecology Model of Health Behavior emphasizes changes in behavior that are influenced by the surrounding environment. The behavior change approach is used in the behavior change approach where the message of behavior change is brought by students to change the behavior of parents and society. Information/messages received on the study table are expected to be received by parents and the community. Information/messages become beliefs and perceptions of truth so that behavior changes occur in parents or society. The behavior of a person or community is determined by the knowledge, attitudes, beliefs, traditions and so on of the person or community concerned. In addition, the availability of facilities, attitudes and behavior of health workers towards health will support and strengthen the formation of behavior. Behavior change is determined by the concept of risk. The determinant of an individual's response to changing behavior is the severity of the risk or disease. In general, if someone knows there is a risk to health then that person will consciously avoid the risk. Health behavior is classified into 3, namely groups:

1. Health maintenance behavior, namely a person's efforts to maintain health so that he does not get sick and efforts to heal if he is sick.
2. Behavior of seeking and using the health service system (health seeking behavior), namely behavior involving efforts or actions of a person when sick and/or accident to try starting from self treatment to seeking treatment abroad.
3. Environmental health behavior, namely the way a person responds to the environment, both physical and socio-cultural environment, so that the environment does not affect his health.

Behavior is an action or activity of the human being itself which has a very broad expanse, including: walking, talking, crying, laughing, working, studying, writing, reading, and so on. From this description it can be concluded that what is meant by human behavior is all activities or human activities, both those that are directly observed, and those that cannot be observed by outsiders (Notoatmodjo, 2003).

According to Skinner quoted by Notoatmodjo (2003), formulates that behavior is a person's response or reaction to stimuli or stimuli from outside. Because this behavior occurs through the process of a stimulus to the organism, and then the organism responds, Skinner's theory is called the "S-O-R" or Stimulus - Organism - Response theory.

According to Notoatmodjo (2003) that seen from the form of response to this stimulus, behavior can be divided into two, namely: (1) closed behavior (converted behavior), namely a person's response to a stimulus in a veiled or closed form (converted). Responses or reactions to this stimulus are still limited to the attention, perception, knowledge, awareness, and attitudes that occur in the person receiving the stimulus, and cannot be clearly observed by other people; and (2) overt behavior, namely a person's response to a stimulus in the form of real or open action. The response to the stimulus is clear in the form of action or practice, which can easily be observed or seen by others.

RESEARCH METHODS

In this study, researchers used descriptive research (descriptive research). With the form of case study research (Case Study), namely research on a symptom or one particular group that is distinctive and unique, and used as a research focus, researchers used a qualitative research approach in this study, so this research used qualitative descriptive research.

The object of research is the nature of the state of an object, person, or being the center of attention and research target (Zuriah, 2009). In this research, the object is teenagers and young people in the urban area of Samarinda from various campuses and schools.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

With the rapid development of social media, it is very easy for teenagers and young people to use social media anytime and anywhere, social media can be said to provide a more severe addiction than alcohol and drugs. The fact is that it is true that social media can make someone addicted and unable to stay away from gadgets for not long enough. Social media, which has no restrictions and controls on its use, has a major influence on changing the behavior of adolescents and youth, especially in urban environments. The negative impact of social media can be seen from the behavior of teenagers and young people who have started to no longer have a culture of good manners, for example from the way they speak, walk in front of their elders, and how they dress. What is very visible from the loss of the culture of polite behavior in adolescents and youth is the culture of

speaking politely towards others, among young people in urban areas more often use words of reproach, humiliation and ridicule when talking to people who are the same age as them rather than using polite words. In contrast to parents aged 40 to 50 years and over, parents aged 40 to 50 years and over often use more subtle language towards each other. This is because teenagers and young people who watch videos use harsh words, criticize and make fun of others easily and normally without warning or warning.

In addition, another negative impact of social media is turning a young teenager into someone who is individualistic. Someone who is active in using social media will no longer care about the state of the environment around them, because when using social media and already feeling preoccupied with the virtual world they have, a person will ignore social interactions with other people in real life and the impact is to create bad relationships between each other. Social media can also cause bad behavior such as prestige and jealousy, these teenagers and youth who have become addicts to social media will always express themselves in the virtual world which is different from themselves in the real world. In addition to showing their perfect side in cyberspace, on social media teenagers and youth can upload their success in achieving or getting something to be proof of their success and show it off to others. It is undeniable that this will trigger jealousy and jealousy among teenagers and young people, so that they are competing to show their success and show it off on social media for the sake of an existence and a show from other people. Jimenez and Morreale (2015) stated that teenagers are less able to interact directly and prefer to see digital images, photos, and even statuses that they write on their social media. Some people in this study also explained that they would be very careful when it comes to personal information that could cause problems or a person's mental health. Furthermore, Kathleen and Council (2011) stated that other problems to be aware of include internet addiction and sleep deprivation simultaneously. Furthermore Muhammad, Yabit and Exzayrani (2019) stated that another impact from the mental side is the emergence of Nomophobia or anxiety disorders that arise when away from the smartphone, symptoms that arise such as fear of not being able to receive information, anxiety if the cellphone cannot be used, or even panic if you don't have a cell phone.

In using social media, it is necessary to have a data package for the operation of this social media so that it is connected to the internet. In fact, the cost of this internet data package is quite expensive and when using the data package to open videos or images contained in social media, social media will not think long enough to refill the data package and ignore other needs that must take precedence.

However, social media also has a positive impact that is very useful for teenagers and young people. With this social media they can easily socialize between individuals without having to worry about time and great distances. With social media, it can help teenagers and young people find new friends who might suit them and can help find old friends who haven't communicated in a long time, so they can connect and add to the bonds of friendship between people. Social media also plays an important role in the formation of positive behavior among adolescents and youth, with various kinds of quality educational information in the formation of an individual's attitude. They can learn the culture of polite behavior from the way of speaking, tone of voice, behavior and other things related to the formation of positive behavior. Because if you only rely on education at school, the psychological formation of a teenager will not really be able to become a well-behaved teenager or youth because of limited time at school in teaching positive behavior and ethics. And also in urban areas nowadays many teenagers and youths use impolite words and anarchic actions easily without thinking too much, so that a young man must be able to take advantage of the use of social media to learn to be a teenager

or youth who has good behavior. among the community, especially in urban areas and become an impulse for teenagers or youth to become teenagers and youth who have good behavior in society.

Table 1: Positive and Negative Impacts of Using Social Media

Positive Impacts	Negative Impacts
Good promotion place and cheap	Disturbing the learning activities of adolescents and youth
The impact of expanding the network of friends The danger of crime Easy communication media The danger of fraud	The impact of expanding the network of friends The danger of crime Easy communication media The danger of fraud
The impact of expanding the network of friends The danger of crime Easy communication media The danger of fraud	The impact of expanding the network of friends The danger of crime Easy communication media The danger of fraud
A place to find useful information Not all social media users are polite. A place to share photos, information, etc. Interfere with family life and communication	A place to find useful information Not all social media users are polite. A place to share photos, information, etc. Interfere with family life and communication
A place to find useful information Not all social media users are polite. A place to share photos, information, etc. Interfere with family life and communication	A place to find useful information Not all social media users are polite. A place to share photos, information, etc. Interfere with family life and communication

Researchers have conducted observations and interviews with several students (adolescents and youth) in the city of Samarinda regarding the current use of social media. Their answers were quite varied. Starting because of the demands, needs and bandwagon in order to say slang. Researchers interviewed 20 people consisting of 10 students and 10 students from various schools and colleges in Samarinda. For students who are in the youth category, they need social media because they need it to make it easier to communicate with their friends, and to access the sources of information they need more easily. It is different with students, they use social media because of demands from the surrounding environment so that they are said to be more sociable, joining in so that they are accepted in their social environment. Psychological changes also appeared. Such as apathy towards the family environment, quite radical rejection because of their time spent surfing social media, as well as significant emotional changes. This proves that the excessive use of social media among young people is of particular concern to a person's psychology, is contradictory and can trigger significant social friction in carrying out their activities.

Based on the results of these interviews, it can be stated that social media can have positive and negative impacts on the social interaction of adolescents and youth. It was stated by Abuk and Iswahyudi (2019) that the positive impacts found included being able to easily obtain information, make it easier to make new friends and broaden existing insights. found on social media that are meaningful and useful for readers. Furthermore, the results of the research reported by Wahyuni (2017) revealed that adolescents/youth use social media as a guideline in social life which is important

for finding information and connecting with friends, interacting with people they like both in friendship and the opposite sex, their old friends. did not meet, until they just met.

In addition to the positive impacts, on the other hand the use of social media has a negative impact, namely it has reduced the intensity of associating and gathering with other people around it, there is a lack of concern for others because they prefer to interact with social media rather than direct interactions in the real world (Abuk and Iswahyudi 2019). Teenagers and youth prefer to spend a long time on gadget screens to interact on social media compared to friends around them. And it is also vulnerable for teenagers to become victims of cyber bullying or online bullying and violence, violations of personal information and others (Chukwuere, J. E. (2021).

CONCLUSION

Social media has facilitated many conveniences for life, and also has a big positive and negative impact on society, especially teenagers and youth.

The positive impact on social interaction is connectivity, the benefits of being connected with anyone regardless of distance, time, religion or country, being able to get the latest news or information quickly, and being able to explore and develop himself with the information he has obtained from social media.

The negative impacts of using social media are lack of caring for others, causing internet addiction, ease of interaction causing lazy socializing and conveying messages directly, impolite and speaking and attitude, lack of self- control for adolescents to maintain their privacy, giving rise to verbal violence, cyberbullying, data theft privacy, sexting to sexual violence, mental health disorders such as Internet Addiction Disorder, Nomophobia and also sleep disorders due to excessive use.

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